

Observations on *Chresiona invalida* (Simon, 1898) (Araneae: Macrobulnidae) from South Africa

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ABSTRACT: Little is known about the genus *Chresiona* Simon, 1903, represented by three South African species, but known only from females. *Chresiona invalida* (Simon, 1898) are free-running ground dwellers that make retreats under rocks and stones. The general morphology of live specimens is discussed, along with notes on their behaviour, distribution, and conservation status.

Keywords: biodiversity, conservation geography distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa)

INTRODUCTION

The Macrobulnidae, represented by 26 genera and about 91 species, occurs worldwide (World Spider Catalog, 2024). The family comprises five genera and 16 species from South Africa including the genus *Chumma* Jocqué, 2001 that were recently described. Little is known about the other four genera *Chresiona* Simon, 1903, *Macrobulnus* Tullgren, 1901, *Obatala* Lehtinen, 1967 and *Pseudauximus* Simon, 1902. They are all listed in the subfamily Macrobulninae (Almeida-Silva, 2013).

Many specimens were sampled and identified as Macrobulninae as part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). The African genera are not yet revised, and still problematic. Most specimens sampled were identified to belong to the genus *Chresiona*. *Chresiona* was first described in the Agelenidae but then transferred to the Amaurobiidae by Lehtinen (1967) and then to the Macrobulnidae by Gorneau *et al.*, (2023). The genus is represented by three South African species but known only from females.

Here, we report on *Chresiona invalida* (Simon, 1898) a species originally described from Pretoria. The general morphology of live specimens is discussed with notes of their behaviour, distribution and conservation status.

METHODS

Voucher specimens sampled ($n=35$) during SANSa surveys are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council (ARC) in Pretoria.

TAXONOMY

Chresiona invalida (Simon, 1898)

Cybaeus invalidus Simon, 1898: 5 (f).

Chresiona invalida Lehtinen, 1967: 222; Dippenaar-Schoeman, *et al.*, 2021: 7.

Diagnostic characteristics: *Female*. Total body size 3–5 mm. The carapace is pale brown with two darker mediolateral bands from the eye region to near the carapace posterior edge (Fig. 1), with a narrow dark band around the edge (Figs 2, 5). The carapace is longer than wide; the cephalic region is only slightly elevated; the fovea is a slight depression. Eight eyes in two rows; anterior median eyes round; smaller than the lateral eyes; posterior lateral and median eyes same size. Abdomen oval, pale cream with dark markings; with deposits of guanine (Fig. 2); abdominal pattern consisting of a narrow median band covering the anterior half of the abdomen; posterior half with a series of 4–5 chevrons; rest abdomen with black spots and bands; abdomen colour variable (Figs 6 & 7); cribellum absent. Legs with dark annulations (Figs 2, 6, 7); three-clawed. Female epigynum has a semi-circular projection with posterior edge thickened (Figs 7–8). Male unknown.

Figure 1. *Chresiona invalida* female from Wyndford Farm near Fouriesburg. Photo: Peter Webb.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA (Fig. 14): Eastern Cape: Addo National Park (-33.32, 25.72); Rhodes (-30.87, 27.94); Thyspunt (-34.19,; 24.71). **Free State:** Wyndford farm, Fouriesburg (-28.61, 28.23). **Gauteng:** Pretoria National Botanical Garden (-25.74, 28.19); Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (-25.8, 28.77); Groenkloof Nature Reserve (-25.47, 28.12); Bronkhorstspruit (-25.82, 28.87). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Sani Pass (-29.62, 29.37). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.949, 29.870). **Mpumalanga:** Ohrigstad (-24.74, 30.58); Machadodorp, Elmshoogte Plantation (-25.66, 30.26); Belfast (-25.69, 30.04). **Western Cape:** Elgin (-34.16, 19.06); Greater Simonsberg Conservancy, Delheim (-33.52, 18.53); Table Mountain National Park (-33.82, 18.48); Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden (33.58, 18.25).

Figure 14. Known distribution of *Chresiona invalida*. Credit: S. Foord.

LIFESTYLE

Chresiona invalida are small, free-running spiders that usually live on the ground under logs, inside leaf litter or moss, or in moss patches on trees. The second author sampled the species very regularly over years from vegetation at the Wyndford Farm in the Free State.

During the SANSA surveys, specimens were sampled with sweeping and beating vegetation but also with pitfall traps from the Fynbos (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2024), Grassland (Haddad *et al.*, 2013), Savanna (Foord *et al.*, 2011), and Thicket biomes.

CONSERVATION

Protected in several protected areas such as Addo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020); Thyspunt (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Wiese, 2022); Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Van Zyl, 2023); Groenkloof Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023b); Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.*, 2019); Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023a) and Table Mountain National Park (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2024). The male of this species has been sampled but still needs to be described. No conservation actions are recommended.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We would like to thank Linda Wiese for her photograph and the late Stefan Foord for the map.

Figures 2–5. *Chresiona invalida*. 2. Female from Bronkhorstspruit, dorsal view. 3–4. Epigyne. 5. Female from Groenkloof Nature Reserve. Photos: 2–5. Peter Webb. 3 ASD. 4. After Lehtinen (1967).

Figures 6–7. *Chresiona invalida* female showing the colour variation. 7. Female from Thyspunt (L. Wiese). 7. Female from Wyndford Farm (Peter Webb).

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